

Assessment of Synthetic Turfgrass Dataset Generation for Divot Detection

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Abstract

Turfgrass divot maintenance is a vital component of sports grounds and golf courses. Precision Turfgrass Management (PTM) uses a variety of smart technologies to manage turfgrass in a sustainable and efficient manner. Deep Learning is an effective way of developing data inspection but requires a large, annotated dataset. This work describes the development of a photo realistic dataset generated using Blender for a turfgrass environment to train deep learning networks to identify anomalies on turfgrass surfaces. Additionally, two colour transfer techniques are analysed, to ensure the synthetic data can closely resemble the real domain data.

Dataset: <https://www.zenodo.org/record/8030582>

Code: <https://github.com/stevefoy/DeepTurfSynth>

Keywords: Imaging, Synthetic data, Turfgrass, Machine Vision, Mobile robotics

1 Introduction

Turfgrass is defined as a plant system that remains green for at least six months of the year while maintaining a continuous dense ground cover during its dormancy period [Carlson et al., 2022]. This type of grass system can be found in numerous locations, from domestic gardens to public parks, sports grounds and golf courses. The benefits of turfgrass systems can be described in terms of functional, recreational, and aesthetic components [Beard and Green, 1994]. One commercial use of turfgrass is in the golf course industry. According to the R&A report in 2021, worldwide there are 148 million acres used for golf with 38,081 golf courses spread among 206 of the 251 countries of the world [Klein, 2021].

Precision Turfgrass Management (PTM) is a data driven approach for the maintenance of Turfgrass resources which includes mowing practices, irrigation, nutrient, pest, and cultivation management [Bell et al., 2013]. A divot refers to a small area of turf or grass that has been displaced from the sports ground [Braun et al., 2020]. A survey paper by Carlson looked at the accuracy of sensors to detect turfgrass performance indicators and the stressors before or during visual symptoms occur on plants. Their finding suggest that there is insufficient training and expertise among superintendents on PTM technology, with a recommendation that future research should focus on automating data collection, processing, and interpretation of data [Carlson et al., 2022].

Figure 1: Turfgrass and semantic mask

This paper explores the generation of turfgrass surface data in a 3-dimensional simulation environment called Blender. A photo realistic image dataset with matching synthetic segmentation annotations has been generated and is openly shared in Zenodo. Secondly, several deep learning benchmarks were developed to measure against prior art using a manually annotated test divot dataset. Furthermore, two augmentation and domain information transfer techniques that can increase the performance of this synthetic dataset to a real domain were proposed. The goal of such work is for smart edge learning and deployment, where turfgrass repairs can be autonomously executed on a robotic platform.

2 Related work

The variability in turfgrass between locations is considerable with multiple factors affecting it, most notably grass species, plant health/soil fertility and cut height. Divots can be defined as texture anomalies; the topic of image-level anomaly detection is not new and extends to many domains and industries. Image-level anomaly detection is a technique used in computer vision to find anomalies or abnormalities in images [Hendrycks et al., 2019]. In 2016 Ding presented some novel work using vision for the grading of turfgrass. Conventionally turfgrass grading on championship golf courses is usually carried out by experts, whereas this project used an Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) to capture the image data. An offline computer vision algorithm was used with a machine learning model to calculate a grade of the turfgrass, unfortunately no data was made public to reproduce the results [Ding et al., 2016].

The collection and annotation of image data is an important process, but it is a labour-intensive task particularly for small objects such as plants and foliage. The work of Waldchen presents a summary of publicly available datasets [Waldchen et al., 2018]. In this work it may be observed that most public datasets are for image classification tasks. The Flourish Project under the TA European Horizon 2020 project had objectives to combine Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) and Unmanned Ground Vehicle (UGV) capabilities for a range of farm management activities. An interesting outcome of the project was a semantically annotated dataset released by the Bonn university Photogrammetry and Robotics group, which used a NDVI camera to help automate the annotation process. This project was focused on sugar beet plants and weeds rather than turfgrass [Liebisch et al., 2016].

In the highly cited work by Skovsen, a novel semi-synthetic dataset called the GrassClover dataset was created with semantic segmentation level annotations. The annotated dataset was developed from several manually collected images. The data has a ground sampling area of 4–8 pixels per millimetre. The generation procedure consisted of cropping plants from images and randomly overlapping these cutouts onto different soil image textures [Skovsen et al., 2019]. The data in the GrassClover dataset was influential to the work in this paper where critical classes (Grass and Soil) could be used to develop baseline algorithm performances. An interesting semi-synthetic (photo realistic) approach was seen in the project titled VisionBlender which was for medical imaging. The project used Blender software as a 3-dimensional (3D) modelling tool for creating scenes and Blender cycles (ray tracing engine) to generate photo realistic data, with accompanying semantic level masks, and depth maps [Cartucho et al., 2021]. An open-source framework for Blender known as the BlenderProc framework, has presented some interesting workflows for creating large-scale urban scenes [Denninger et al., 2023].

3 Approach taken

Taking inspiration from the GrassClover dataset and VisionBlender, the objective of this project was to develop a photo realistic dataset with annotations for turfgrass. A 3D turfgrass scene in its simplistic form consisted of a plane of soil with grass objects distributed across it. When rendering images of the dataset at 4k resolution, a full grass scene had in the region of ~200,000 grass leaves in a scene. Blender's new node-based workflow allowed for efficient and randomised rotations and scale and density

of grass assets on the various soil textures. To achieve photo realism both proprietary and custom grass leaf assets were used in the generation. Additionally soil and dirt textures were from 4K to 8K resolution [Price, 2023]. Distribution of this open database keeps within copyright restrictions. The texture incorporated in the rendered scenes used RGB textures, normal maps, displacement maps, and specular maps. The Blender Cycles ray tracing engine was used and resulted in rendering times per image of ~ 1 minute on a NVIDIA RTX4090 GPU with OptiX enabled. The virtual camera in the scene was setup with a 26mm focal length at 4K resolution to mimic both a modern smart phone and the GrassClover dataset with the objective to validate this data against the state of the art.

An additional consideration in these scenes was the creation of divots. On a golf course the divot width can vary depending on the golf club, the swing technique, and the type of turf. A divot caused by iron shots with standard-sized golf clubs tend to range from around 2.5 to 7.6 centimetres in width [Turgeon, 1991]. Based on this knowledge, a weight map or alternatively known as a vertex weight map were created in blender for the creation of divots. These widths were considered when creating the divots, so nothing was created less than 2.5 cm. These weight textures were incorporated with a geometry node workflow. When divots occur on a grass turf there is an additional deformation to the planer topology, and this was modelled in Blender as a 10mm offset.

3.1 Semantic Segmentation data

To generate a semantic segmentation mask in blender, a custom blender composition Nodetree was required. The Nodetree can take each rendered pixel in the rendered image and associate a Pass Index number with a colour to build up a 16bit colour mask (semantic segmentation mask). Objects created in blender are made up of meshes and have a Material Shader associated that give the mesh colour. A feature in blender software is the ability to associate a custom Pass Index number for each Material Shader. The strategy taken in this work was to add a sub-string that was representative of the annotation group, as a Blender object can have multiple Material Shaders. Let us take for example a grass Material Shader named as *Grass_Rye_Leaves*. This means the sub-string *Grass* can be found in the Material Shader name. A Blender Python script was developed to associate lists of Material Shader names or sub-strings of the Shader names as class definitions. An additional post processing step using a Python script converted the 16 bit RGB mask into a simple 8 bit monochrome image. These images are more efficient in deep learning frameworks such as PyTorch.

4 Datasets

4.1 Turfgrass test dataset

Images of divots were collected from a golf course with a smart phone camera (Samsung Galaxy A70); the images had a resolution of 4032x3024 and a focal length of 26mm. The images were captured at a handheld height of one meter over the turfgrass surface with the camera facing parallel. A simple calibration procedure using a small target 56 x 87mm was used to estimates that there was 3.6 pixels per millimetre ground coverage. The manual annotation process was carried out using GIMP imaging software. During the initial research a number of semantic segmentation networks were trained on the GrassClover Dataset, see Figure 3. The positive results

Figure 2: Probability mask in GIMP

achieved were utilized to support the manual annotation process, where the soil class matrix of the Soft-Max layer was imported into GIMP. A coloured visualization of this map can be seen in the Figure 2. A total of 90 images were annotated and saved as a multi-layer TIFF file which could be processed by a Python script to split the images into 400x400 pixel patches to form the test set for a synthetic generated turfgrass. This resulted in a test dataset of 3864 images. Although the results obtained from testing on this dataset may exhibit a slight bias towards the GrassClover dataset, the primary objective was to establish a robust test set for our own synthetic dataset.

4.2 Synthetic Turfgrass dataset

The blender virtual camera was rendered at 4032x3024 and placed at 1 metre above the surface resulting in four pixels per millimetre, with no perspective distortion in the lens. The generated data created in blender had matching annotations as detailed in the earlier sections. A Python script split the images into 400x400 pixel patches, resulting in a total of 6510 images, with 10 % used as a validation set during training.

5 Training

In this section a quantitative evaluation of the experiments and a benchmark on our dataset using a number of common DL architectures is presented [Wang et al., 2022]. The initial baseline created used the public GrassClover dataset. The Grassclover dataset paper mentions the use of FCN8 and a subset of their dataset with no explicit details. The paper’s class intersection over union (IoU) scores are as follows grass, white clover, red clover, weeds and soil, [64.4, 59.5, 72.6, 39.1, 39.0]. Similar results were established using a FCN8 + VGG16 encoder [0.53, 0.59, 0.71 ,0.56, 0.64, 0.50] with a PyTorch version on a validation set. The focus was on two classes - grass and soil, in the training of our synthetic dataset.

Table 1: Trained on GrassClover and deployed on a real world turfgrass dataset

Model	Object Class					
	grass	white clover	red clover	weeds	soil	clover other
DeeplabV3+	0.58	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.54	0.0
PSPNet	0.13	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.18	0.0
FCN8	0.49	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.37	0.0
UNet	0.35	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.17	0.0

Figure 3: Result on test image using DeepLabV3+, trained on GrassClover dataset

5.1 Colour augmentation

We observed that a number of test images encountered performance issues resulting in low class IOU scores during the development work. These images had a slight colour variation and by visualizing the histograms of these problematic images, we could prove that there were auto-white balance (AWB) abnormalities. The AWB feature is active by default on most cameras, giving a colour temperature to the captured raw data and a neutral appearance to the human eye. AWB, or Auto White Balance, strives to emulate the phenomenon of colour constancy observed in the human visual system, particularly under different lighting conditions. Consequently, one can observe the objects in the scene as accurately reflecting the chromatic properties of the captured scene [Buzzelli et al., 2023]. To mitigate against these issues is to capture the image using a manual white balance mode or alternatively capturing in raw mode and correcting after.

Figure 4: Colour transfer, Raw to target synthetic

Trials were conducted using the PyTorch ColourJitter transformation module for brightness (0.1-0.5), contrast (0.1-0.5), saturation (0.1-0.5), and hue (0-0.1). Unfortunately, no significant improvements on class IOU scores were achieved on the problematic test images. The informative work of Afifi and Brown on issues related to AWB was used to provide a colour augmentation strategy to our synthetic dataset [Afifi and Brown, 2019]. The augmented images had a noticeable realistic colour compared to using PyTorch colour jitter augmentations. Another colour augmentation explored in this paper was a colour transfer technique pioneered by Reinhard, which involves the transfer the colour distribution from one image (source) to training images (destination) [Reinhard et al., 2001]. Several real images captured from the smart phone that consisted of just turfgrass were used as the source set and this augmentation strategy was distributed into the training at a rate of 10 % of the dataset, and only on images that had > 95 % pixels in the foliage class.

5.2 Training and Evaluation

The segmentation models were trained on synthetic data and tested on the manually annotated divot dataset. Four common DL architectures were selected to establish our baselines: DeeplabV3+ with Resnet101 backbone, PSPNet with ResNet101 backbone, FCN8 with VGG16 backbone and UNet. Networks with Resnet and VGG16 backbones were initialized with PyTorch ImageNet weights. During the training PSPNet and DeepLabV3+ architectures had the encoder and batch normalization layers frozen, resulting in the decoder layers learning the segmentation classes. The mean RGB image and standard deviation were calculated in the synthetic data set and used to normalise FCN8 and UNet models during training and deployment on the test set, while other defaults used were ImageNets. All the findings pre-

sented in this paper were obtained using the PyTorch 2 framework, incorporating the **crossEntropyLoss** function and employing a class weighting strategy. The assigned weights for grass and soil, [1.5, 9.5] respectively, were computed in accordance with the Enet article [Paszke et al., 2016]. One challenge with generating a high-quality annotation is that they can be too accurate with small objects annotations, some of which looks like salt and pepper noise. An optional parameter in the loss function used was **label_smoothing** at 0.2 which improved generalization. Adam was used as the optimiser on all the training. Table 2 presents the performance results achieved after training these networks only on synthetic data for a duration of 25 epochs, followed by their deployment on the test dataset.

Table 2: Comparisons of semantic segmentation results on turfgrass dataset, (**ST**: Source to destination image transfer augmentation, **AWB**: auto-white balance augmentation)

Model	Pixel Accuracy	MIoU	Classes	
			Foliage	Divot
DeeplabV3+	0.97	0.72	0.97	0.46
DeeplabV3+ + ST	0.98	0.81	0.98	0.64
DeeplabV3+ + AWB	0.99	0.82	0.98	0.66
PSPNet	0.95	0.64	0.95	0.34
PSPNet + ST	0.97	0.68	0.97	0.39
PSPNet + AWB	0.97	0.71	0.97	0.45
FCN8	0.97	0.70	0.97	0.44
FCN8 + ST	0.98	0.77	0.98	0.55
FCN8 + AWB	0.98	0.84	0.99	0.68
UNET	0.98	0.79	0.98	0.59
UNET + ST	0.98	0.81	0.98	0.64
UNET + AWB	0.99	0.83	0.98	0.68

Figure 5: Result on test image using UNET + ST, trained on our synthetic dataset

6 Discussion

This paper described the development of a test dataset and training of a number of segmentation networks to create a baseline using the public GrassClover data. A common smartphone camera was used as the test system; this choice imposes a hardware limitation but this is common across many similar vision systems. The synthetic dataset were trained across these similar DL models and presented positive results. A number of colour augmentation strategies were presented to address colour inconsistency that exists between the synthetic dataset and the real world test dataset. AWB augmentation strategy

has shown positive increases in performance, furthermore the colour transfer algorithm has produced visually impressive results and has led to an interesting increase in performance.

7 Conclusions and Future Work

This work has shown that this blender simulation workflow can be used to address the challenges of annotation where there is a high object count such as grass in a turfgrass scene. The study benchmarks have additionally proven that this synthetic data can be used in the training of deep learning networks, with benchmarks presented against a real dataset. There are several directions possible in research but a natural progression with this blender pipeline is for the analysis for turfgrass scenes at different camera angles to explore the possibilities of turfgrass and divot topology mapping.

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